

Fact Sheet for policy-makers, agroecology organizations and researchers

The added value of a European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures

Summary

- ALL-Ready synthesised the potential added value of a European Network of Agroecology Living Labs (LLs) and Research Infrastructures (RIs).
- The synthesis is based on an analysis of the key challenges and needs of agroecology LLs and RIs integrating insights from mapping activities, workshops of the ALL-Ready pilot network of LLs & RIs as well as interviews with a selection of LLs, RIs and funding organisations.

Source: ALL-Ready Project

Problem

Agroecology LLs and RIs face a variety of challenges related to the operationalisation and the management of their research and innovation activities. Access to funding is a common challenge for most Living Labs and Research Infrastructures. Important funding gaps exist for training and demonstration as well as maintaining infrastructure and networks.

Solution

The complexity of the challenges to be addressed in transitions of farming and food systems to agroecology, requires concerted and integrated efforts of science, practice and society, as well as policy at European scale. A future European Network of Agroecology LLs and RIs can provide such a coordinated, large-scale initiative for agroecology transitions.

Benefits

Key benefits from participating and funding a European Network of Agroecology LLs and RIs include strengthened networking and collaboration, enhanced portfolios of research and innovation activities, synergies between private and public funding, and strengthened knowledge creation, exchange and diffusion resulting in further improvements in the governance of Agroecology LLs and RIs.

Strengthened networking and collaboration promotes co-creation of knowledge and engagement of stakeholders in transitions to agroecology.

Main results

A European Network of Agroecology LLs and RIs is a major component of the EU Partnership "Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures". It has the potential to support inclusive place-based innovation that accelerates the transition to agroecology at the local, regional and national levels across Europe. Utilizing this potential requires the development and implementation of a sustainable long-term strategy and implementation plan for the governance,

funding and activities of the European Network to contribute to effectively filling remaining knowledge gaps, while at the same time boosting real-life and place-based approaches.

Practical recommendations

Implementing and managing the European Network to reach the entire value chain, from seed producers to consumers, will promote solutions for accelerating transitions to agroecology and support the creation of circular and solidarity economies.

Further information

ALL-READY DELIVERABLE

- The ALL-Ready project deliverables can be found here: <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/communication/deliverables.html> (after the embargo period)
- The Deliverable report on the added value of a European Network of Agroecology LLs and RIs can be accessed here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7105206>

WEBLINKS

- European Partnership under Horizon Europe Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/research-area/agriculture-forestry-and-rural-areas/ecological-approaches-and-organic-farming/partnership-agroecology_en

Source: ÖMKI

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About ALL-Ready: ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (RI) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

Publisher: Thünen-Institute of Farm Economics & FiBL Europe

Authors: Gerald Schwarz, May Hobeika, Isidora Stojacic, Bastian Gödel, Rocio Canio Perez

Contact: gerald.schwarz@thuenen.de

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Project website: www.all-ready-project.eu

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